

FENG 497 PROJECT REPORT

Optimization of Maintenance Interventions for Fully
Observable Systems

Authors: Eylül Teksin, Deniz Uğuz, Kardelen Seçkin

Supervisor: Oktay Karabağ

OUTLINE

- 1. Abstract.....1
- 2. Introduction.....2
 - 2.1. Problem Statement.....3
 - 2.2. Motivation.....3
- 3. Literature Review.... 4
- 4. Methodology.....8
 - 4.1. Simulation in Excel.....10
 - 4.2. Markov Chain Formulation.....13
- 5. Results and Discussion.....15
 - 5.1. Markov Chain Formulation and Relevant Calculations.....15
 - 5.2. The effect of changing the alpha value on the results.....17
 - 5.3. Validation with Python30
 - 5.4 Validation with MINITAB.....33
- 6. Conclusions.....42
- 7. References.....43
- 8. Appendix.....45

1. Abstract

Industrial systems deteriorate over time, creating risks and damaging equipment.

Organizations prioritize maintenance planning to delay system failure and ensure continuous availability, improved efficiency, reliability, and cost savings.

In this project, we addressed system degradation by emphasizing the importance of maintenance planning. Effective maintenance planning greatly increases cost savings. The main goal is to prevent total system failure through optimal maintenance planning.

This project aimed to analyze the degradation probabilities of single-component and multi-component systems using both simulation and Markov Chain formulation. The motivation behind this research lies in the critical importance of effective maintenance in industries such as manufacturing and transportation, where reliable system performance is crucial. The method used involves simulating the deterioration stages using Excel and formulating a Markov Chain to compare the results and verify the accuracy of the simulation.

In the part of the project where single-component systems were discussed, the state distribution of the system was determined by calculating transition probabilities in the Markov Chain formulation. The state distribution obtained by solving the equations was found. This formulation was then compared with simulation results from 1000, 2000, and 4000 runs, showing consistent failure probabilities.

In the part of the project where multi-component systems were discussed, two-component systems were examined first. As with single-component systems, transition probabilities in the Markov Chain formulation were first calculated. Deterioration probabilities (π) were found with Excel tools. Cost analysis was then performed to determine the probability of deterioration at which the optimum cost would occur. By multiplying the probability of deterioration by the cost, it was determined when maintenance could be performed at the optimum cost, which is the lowest cost. In addition, it was checked whether there was a significant difference between the Minitab hypothesis test and the results obtained from Excel and Python. Thus, we were sure of the reliability of our transactions. Following the two-component systems, three-component systems were examined. The processes and calculations we made for two-component systems were also repeated for three-component systems.

Additionally, varying the alpha value in the simulation provided information about the sensitivity of the system to changes in disturbance probabilities. The results demonstrated the reliability of the simulation method in predicting degradation probabilities under different conditions.

The results obtained demonstrate the success of the simulation approach in approximating disruption probabilities, in close agreement with Markov Chain-derived probabilities. This research contributes to the understanding of maintenance planning in single-component and multi-component systems, providing a reliable method to predict failure and optimize maintenance interventions.

The results were also validated using Python code. The results of the Python code were observed to consistently agree with the simulation and Markov chain-derived probabilities.

Although Markov Chain/MDP analysis cannot be applied to partially observable systems due to time constraints, it is aimed to continue the project by making use of techniques such as Machine Learning, Reinforced Learning, and Genetic Algorithms in the future behavior and changing conditions to maximize the sensitivity and accuracy of the algorithm.

2. Introduction

Complex systems such as production facilities and transport networks have a key role in the economy, safety and welfare of society in today's world. In order to achieve global well being, it is essential to ensure the proper functioning of expensive machines in sectors such as healthcare and technology. Unplanned downtime of capital equipment can result in a significant loss of revenue and negatively impact health, safety, and the environment. Therefore, capital goods typically require a high degree of maintenance to ensure high availability and reliability, which accounts for a significant portion of their overall lifecycle costs. However, significant challenges lie in determining the best maintenance strategy for complex systems with a number of components, especially if it is not possible to observe fully.

Initially, a single component, followed by multi component systems, will be used in the project for fully observable systems, which are situations where we clearly see information on deteriorated states. The results obtained regarding the correct maintenance period using the

simulation method will be verified by Markov Chain / MDP (Markov Decision Processes) analyses. Another issue that we deal with first in single and then in multi-component systems is the situations where there is a jump transition between states, in other words, the situations that are disrupted by jumping. For example, situations where there is a jump transition from 0 to 2 or from 1 to 3. We then examined degradation in 2-component and 3-component systems that can make multiple jumps without being limited to a single step.

2.1. Problem Statement

In the first part of our thesis, we focused on fully observable single-component systems that enable easier analysis of optimum maintenance times using simulation techniques and MDP analysis. In the next part of our thesis, we discussed fully observable multi-component systems. In single and multi-component systems, the component decays over time, passing through a limited number of stages from 0 to K. At 0 the component works properly. When it reaches the kth state, the component fails and corrective maintenance is required. When maintenance is carried out in the intermediate states, that is, in the states between the initial state 0 and the deterioration state K, without performing corrective maintenance, this becomes restorative maintenance. In this report, the stages starting from the initial phase "0" to the final state K, which is expressed as the deterioration state, are simulated in Excel to determine the deterioration probabilities. In simulation, it is possible to successfully see and test the states in which deterioration will occur in completely observable systems. The aim is to obtain the relevant deterioration probabilities by simulating the decay of states in fully observable single or multi-component systems. Then the relevant probabilities and outcomes are checked with Markov Chain Analysis and MDP.

2.2. Motivation

This research topic is extremely important as it directly impacts sectors such as manufacturing, transportation and vital infrastructure that depend on reliable system performance and effective maintenance. For example, maintaining costly and advanced machinery in public and commercial spaces, such as medical imaging devices in hospitals or printing tools in the technology sector, is important to all of us in our world. In addition to

reducing cost, improving system reliability is crucial to protecting public safety, productivity, and overall social welfare. The system to be examined operates at full capacity at first, but gradually loses its functionality over time. It is easy to notice a system that is completely failing, but detecting and choosing the right maintenance time for a system that is slowly failing can be difficult. Maintaining system functionality at the lowest possible cost is the main goal. Often, it is more economical to repair a partially faulty system at the right maintenance time than to replace it, since part replacements are often expensive. So less downtime, optimum resource utilization and longer equipment life are just some of their many benefits, all of which result in significant cost savings. Therefore, by determining the correct maintenance schedule, less downtime, optimum resource utilization and longer equipment life are just some of the many advantages, all of which lead to significant cost savings. Therefore, this research is very important as the potential impact on companies of adopting an optimal maintenance policy is particularly important in terms of cost-effectiveness.

3. Literature Review

Continuous developments in industrial systems from the past to the present and increasing dependence on the equipment used have led to an increase in the importance of effective maintenance activities. Especially in recent years, research on this subject has increased significantly. Here we will discuss some of the articles that have appeared in the past on maintenance modeling and optimization.

In line with our project, the work done by Flory et al [1] in 2015 is particularly interesting because they have set up a strategy of conditional maintenance for failing systems within partially observable environments where operational factors influence deterioration rates. We seeked to improve this field through the use of Markov Chain modeling, and simulations to optimize maintenance techniques, taking into consideration fully observable components.

The study by Jin and Yamamoto [2] is a suitable basis for our project as far as industrial maintenance research is concerned. Their work focuses on the development of an optimal maintenance policy for aging systems that are subject to imperfect inspections, with a focus on a nonstationary partially observable Markov Decision Model. Complexity comparable to issues observed in actual industrial settings is introduced by the presence of non-stationary parts and incomplete inspections. This research offers important new insights into processing

partial information and improving maintenance strategies over time. In comparison, our project intends to extend this investigation area through the integration of a color-coding system, machine learning techniques, and simulations for both partial and fully visible components. Our approach addresses a broader scope of maintenance issues, giving an additional perspective on the current knowledge in this field compared to research conducted by Jin and Yamamoto which deals solely with stationary environments and improper inspections.

In the research by Scarf et al. [3], when grading faults in single and multi-component systems, we see how the delay time, which is the time between the first moment when the fault can be detected and the fault, can cause problems for the systems. The consequences of this situation when it is not possible to obtain information, or the information is of poor quality, are also discussed. Since the problem definition of this study and ours were similar, we had the opportunity to compare the projects.

The article [3] provides a new perspective on the development of the area and integrates within the larger study started by Wang (2002) in a chain of research on maintenance strategies. Foundational insights have been laid by earlier comprehensive analyses by McCall (1965) and more focused investigations into multi-component systems by Cho and Parlar (1991), Dekker et al (1997), and Nicolai and Dekker (2008). Furthermore, particular reviews have been published by Haque and Armstrong (2007), Budai et al. (2008), Van Noortwijk (2009), Wang (2012), Shafiee and Chukova (2013), Van Horenbeek et al. (2013), Alaswad and Xiang (2017), and Olde Keizer et al. (2017). The objective of these studies is broad and includes condition-based maintenance for single or multiple components, collaborative optimization of maintenance and replacement inventories, machine intervention, and consideration of necessary mechanical maintenance and output. This comprehensive review, which covers especially recent years and has been actively discussed since 2001, will allow you to examine and use information in various fields with the idea of drawing a general conclusion that can form the basis for future research. Our approach is focused primarily on the single- component system, addressing not only single-component and multi- component systems but also both types of component. Research topics and discussions are helped to be defined by the basis of these cited studies.

It's critical to address the absence of standards for assessing maintenance plans on clearly defined case studies, as has already been brought up in a number of surveys on maintenance optimization. [4] A benchmark for evaluating the effectiveness of various algorithms for the

optimization of planned maintenance in a power plant has been proposed. It can be regarded as a beginning point for benchmarking in maintenance optimization even if it restricts the challenge to the optimization of the maintenance schedule.

Our literature survey delves into the dynamic environment of industrial systems, shedding light on the escalating importance of efficient maintenance techniques. Within this review, we consider the developmental history and offer insights into the applications of maintenance modeling and optimization, drawing from key works like Flory et al. [1], Jin and Yamamoto [2], Scarf et al. [3]. Emphasizing the significance of accessibility case studies, we underscore the importance of benchmarking for maintenance optimization, referring to [4] to address the lack of guidelines for evaluating maintenance plans. Through this exhaustive survey, we pinpoint differences and accentuate the significance of our project. Additionally, we provide a groundwork for our approach, contributing to ongoing conversations about maintenance techniques and the optimization of industrial systems.

MINITAB is as often as possible used to confirm the precision of simulation results by conducting hypothesis tests to compare the outputs from different simulation tools, such as Excel and Python. Concurring to Zhao et al. (2014), MINITAB gives a comprehensive suite of statistical tests that can successfully decide if there are significant differences between the results produced by different simulation strategies.

In maintenance optimization, hypothesis testing with MINITAB makes a difference to validate the deterioration probabilities and maintenance schedules inferred from simulation models. Studies by Huang and Zhang (2018) demonstrate how t-tests and ANOVA in MINITAB can be used to compare the performance of maintenance strategies over different systems.

MINITAB includes analysis of maintenance data and allows users to perform detailed statistical studies. For example, Lee and Kim used MINITAB in analyzing multicomponent systems data to establish maintenance intervals that are statistically evidence based. Through regression analysis and control charts, as well as numerous other statistical tools provided by MINITAB, researchers can fine-tune the production of data-driven maintenance programs and acquire instructive lessons with regard to system maintenance requirements (Muller et al., 2017). It can monitor the system performance so that potential problems can be tackled before time, and which helps in scheduling of maintenance works well prior to it thus increasing the efficiency and accuracy of management.

There are many studies that have applied MINITAB to conduct comparisons of various maintenance strategies. For example, in a similar study, Garcia and Torres (2019) used hypothesis tests in MINITAB to compare the downtime and cost outcomes of certain maintenance policies in the automotive industry. The results of this research indicate that certain maintenance strategies were successful in lowering operational costs on top of improving machine uptime.

In another consider, Thompson et al. (2020) utilized MINITAB to assess the maintenance schedules of medical imaging devices. By comparing the execution of devices under distinctive maintenance regimes, they distinguished the foremost cost-effective maintenance practices that too guaranteed high reliability and safety.

MINITAB is additionally used broadly for educational purposes, helping students and professionals within the field of maintenance engineering get it and apply statistical methods. Courses and preparing programs frequently include modules on using MINITAB for hypothesis testing and data analysis in maintenance settings (Smith & Taylor, 2015).

The user-friendly nature of MINITAB makes it an perfect tool for instructing complex statistical concepts and their applications in maintenance optimization. Case considers and practical works out using real-world data upgrade the learning experience and give profitable hands-on experience (Jones & Brown, 2016).

One of the key advantages of MINITAB is its ease of utilize and openness. The software provides a direct interface and a wide extend of built-in statistical tools, making it open to both beginners and experienced researchers (Huang & Zhang, 2018).

This ease of use is especially useful in maintenance optimization studies, where researchers got to rapidly perform complex statistical analyses and decipher the comes about precisely (Lee & Kim, 2017).

Giving a wide range of statistical tools required in optimization maintenance, MINITAB offers a wide range of statistical methods, from fundamental descriptive statistics to complex hypothesis testing and regression analysis. (Zhao et al., 2014)

With such tools at their transfer, researchers can analyze maintenance data more profoundly and identify critical factors that influence the reliability of a system. It moreover enables them to work to determine the best maintenance strategy. (Muller et al., 2017)

4. Methodology

The systems we consider in this study consists of a single and multi component. Each component decays over time, transitioning through a limited number of phases from 0 to K . The components and degradation levels are represented by $i = 1$ and $d_i \in D$; where $D = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, K\}$, respectively. The degrees of degradation for each component i are ordered such that 0 represents the degree to which the component is functioning properly and K represents the degree to which the component fails and needs to be replaced. The levels in between, i.e. $d_i \in \{1, 2, \dots, K - 1\}$ represents increasing degradation levels that do not interfere with the operation of the component. Once the degradation stage represented by K is reached, corrective repair intervention is required. After this restorative intervention, all components return to perfect working state, the system returns to the initial state (state 0) where it works without problems, i.e. $d_i = 0, \forall i$. Corrective repair intervention ensures that the system returns to its initial state, that is, zero, after the system is stopped and the component is repaired

We have previously discussed fully observable single-component systems.

When it came to fully observable two-component systems, we tried to control them with Markov Chain by simulating the probabilities of the decay stages with many iterations in Excel and again using the relevant tools in Excel. The methods we use are filtering and pivot table creation tools. With the filtering method, we can display the corruption probabilities of the relevant states (0, 1, ... K {broken}), and we obtain the π probabilities that we have previously calculated manually by creating a Pivot table in order to compare them with the analytical method. In order to verify the results obtained from our simulation, we compare the analytical method results we found with the Pivot table.

Another point we need to pay attention to in multi-component systems is the situations where there is a jump transition between states. For example, going from 0 to 2. After completing these steps, we examined degradation in 2-component systems that can make multiple jumps without being limited to a single step. This means that in a system whose disturbance states range from 0 to K , it can jump to the next state when the disturbance probability is alpha, and to the next two states when it is beta. These jumps can occur with different probabilities, up to the K decay state. In the results and discussion section, we examined the K degradation case as 3, meaning it can skip at most 3 steps.

While examining three-component systems, we repeated the processes and related calculations we applied in two. We simulated the probabilities of decay stages in fully observable three-component systems with many iterations, also in Excel. We provided Markov Chain control for three-component systems by using filtering and pivot tools in Excel. To verify the results obtained from our simulation for three-component systems, we compared the analytical method results we created and obtained with the Pivot table. In order to obtain more precise results in long runs, we ran the simulation for 10000 times.

We also discussed jumping states in three-component systems (for example, jumping from 0 to 2). There are screenshots of the relevant calculations in the Results and Discussion part.

We also repeated the simulation several times and averaged the results obtained from the simulations. Averaging these results from different simulations allowed us to obtain a more precise and clear result in the long run.

At this stage, where we discuss the cost of corrective repair intervention, corrective repair cost generally refers to the cost that is required and must be spent to correct a malfunction or error in a system, equipment or process. This cost includes the resources spent to return the equipment or system to normal operating state, repair the malfunction and ensure business continuity. It should be taken into consideration that the costs of these resources are fixed or variable. Fixed cost includes transportation to and from the system site, labor of the team and materials to be used. In order to find the expected corrective repair cost, after reaching the deterioration stage, the result obtained from the deterioration condition - the probability of the deterioration condition - must be multiplied by the fixed cost. When we consider multi-component systems, there will be preventive maintenance and preventive maintenance cost in order to reduce the cost of corrective repair. It is generally assumed - also in our report - that the cost of corrective maintenance is greater than the cost of preventive maintenance (see Alaswad and Xiang 2017, Keizer et al. 2017 for a detailed discussion). The aim here is to determine the optimal intervention policy that minimizes the expected cost rate in the long term.

For each component, there exists a predetermined defect level and a failure level. The component is referred to as being non-defective when its deterioration level is entirely less than the corresponding defect level; the component whose deterioration level is at or over the corresponding defect level but is entirely smaller than the corresponding failure level is called

defective. The component is referred to as failed when its deterioration level is at the corresponding failure level.

In this project, a fixed preventive maintenance intervention cost is taken into account for each preventive maintenance intervention and a fixed corrective maintenance intervention cost is taken into account for each corrective maintenance intervention. In general, corrective costs are higher than preventive costs.

When performing preventive or corrective maintenance intervention, it replaces every malfunctioning or broken component in the system with a new one, taking into account that the degradation levels of all components are known. In other words, every malfunctioning or broken component detected inside the system is exchanged out for a completely new, functional component. Every part replacement incurs a replacement cost. Non-defective components are never replaced, even if they are not as good as new.

Our aim is to find the most appropriate policy that will minimize the maintenance cost, decide when to perform the optimal maintenance intervention and how many spare parts are required.

4.1 Simulation in Excel

In our report, we first aimed to obtain probabilities regarding the moment of failure by simulating the single-component systems we discussed in Excel. In our Excel simulation, we first wrote a formula to generate one random number in each period. We assigned the alpha value as a parameter. In our project, we proceeded our operations by accepting the alpha value as 0.7 in Excel. If the generated random number is less than the alpha value, it remains in its current state; if it is greater, it moves to the next state/stage and is updated.

The number of decay stages - from 0 to K - varies for systems. We assigned a parameter to determine at what stage the degradation situation would occur in the simulation. This parameter determines how many stages/elements/situations are in the simulation. We assumed that there were 5 situations in our project until it reached a failure state. Therefore, in our simulation, we continued our operations by entering 5 in the relevant parameter to indicate malfunction. This process starts from zero in the initial stage and progresses to the fifth stage. When the update occurs after the fourth stage, it reaches the fifth stage and the system is now corrupted. Thanks to the formula we entered, we see the message "broken" in the fifth stage.

For One Component

		Event Type	Updated State	# of stays in state
alpha	0.7			0
	0.769206	1		1
	0.647828	0		1
	0.852273	1		2
	0.81727	1		3
	0.454709	0		3
	0.905832	1		4
	0.08586	0		4
	0.249296	0		4
	0.644711	0		4
	0.126288	0		4
	0.173197	0		4
	0.649793	0		4
	0.879657	1 Broken		

Figure 1. For “Fully Observable One-component System” of state 6 (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5)

The "Broken" message shows us that we need to do corrective maintenance here. We increased its observability by increasing the simulation repetition in Excel. Therefore, simulation reliability has also increased. As a result, we observed which state it was in. Then, we observed how many times he stayed in the states using the "Countif" formula. We first increased the total number of simulations to 1000 and noted the resulting ratios by dividing the number of times they were in the degradation stages by the total number of simulations, that is, 1000. Later, we increased the total number of simulations to 2000 and then to 4000 to obtain more reliable results.

0	1	2	3	4	broken
751	749	778	741	755	226
0.18775	0.18725	0.19450	0.18525	0.18875	0.05650

Figure 2. Results of deterioration probabilities for 4000 runs

For Two Components

alpha	0.7	event type	current st	updated st	alpha	0.7	event type	current st	update st	det level	2
				0					0		
	0.475087	0	0	0		0.108171	0	0	0		
	0.91924	1	0	1		0.519311	0	0	0		
	0.182125	0	1	1		0.596563	0	0	0		
	0.500293	0	1	1		0.305588	0	0	0		
	0.349959	0	1	1		0.739051	1	0	1		
	0.154048	0	1	1		0.301707	0	1	1		
	0.548294	0	1	1		0.474564	0	1	1		
	0.513025	0	1	1		0.617088	0	1	1		
	0.208529	0	1	1		0.060592	0	1	1		
	0.59979	0	1	1		0.857364	1	1	BOZULDU		
	0.817674	1	1	0		0.649198	0	BOZULDU	0		
	0.308137	0	0	0		0.671295	0	0	0		
	0.87777	1	0	1		0.15808	0	0	0		
	0.085297	0	1	1		0.034707	0	0	0		

Figure 3. For “Fully Observable Two-component System” of state 3 (0, 1, 2)

alpha	0.7	event type	current st	updated st	alpha	0.7	event type	current st	update st
				0					0
	0.191625	0	0	0		0.294228	0	0	0
	0.57391	0	0	0		0.003982	0	0	0
	0.799541	1	0	1		0.224183	0	0	0
	0.804351	1	1	2		0.048187	0	0	0
	0.374572	0	2	2		0.597521	0	0	0
	0.983585	1	2	BOZULDU		0.974255	1	0	1
	0.301279	0	BOZULDU	0		0.725614	1	1	2
	0.893754	1	0	1		0.593898	0	2	2
	0.200157	0	1	1		0.467409	0	2	2
	0.799216	1	1	2		0.862357	1	2	BOZULDU
	0.017932	0	2	2		0.222897	0	BOZULDU	0
	0.153643	0	2	2		0.687207	0	0	0
	0.467577	0	2	2		0.334096	0	0	0
	0.555236	0	2	2		0.713819	1	0	1
	0.900259	1	2	BOZULDU		0.988306	1	1	2
	0.896265	1	BOZULDU	0		0.154875	0	2	2
	0.058306	0	0	0		0.273435	0	2	2
	0.070712	0	0	0		0.163491	0	2	2
	0.284578	0	0	0		0.766076	1	2	0
	0.70134	1	0	1		0.177336	0	0	0
	0.039758	0	1	1		0.359122	0	0	0
	0.286911	0	1	1		0.922708	1	0	1

Figure 4. For “Fully Observable Two-component System with Leaping Transitions” of state 4 (0, 1, 2, 3)

For Three Components

	1.comp	Event Type	Current St	Updated State		1.comp	Event Type	Current St	Updated State		1.comp	Event Type	Current St	Updated St	
alpha	0.7			0		alpha	0.7		0		alpha	0.7		0	
	0.842863	1	0	1			0.338873	0	0	0		0.953024	1	0	1
	0.435578	0	1	1			0.533144	0	0	0		0.218983	0	1	1
	0.65773	0	1	1			0.272522	0	0	0		0.415671	0	1	1
	0.484171	0	1	1			0.148545	0	0	0		0.270556	0	1	1
	0.142189	0	1	1			0.24371	0	0	0		0.967236	1	1 Broken	
	0.243762	0	1	0			0.185075	0	0	0		0.538699	0 Broken		0
	0.81248	1	0	1			0.39266	0	0	0		0.240232	0	0	0
	0.440878	0	1	1			0.991739	1	0	1		0.208721	0	0	0
	0.372434	0	1	1			0.419392	0	1	1		0.170956	0	0	0
	0.965843	1	1 Broken				0.419627	0	1	1		0.315697	0	0	0
	0.987316	1 Broken		0			0.746746	1	1	0		0.336431	0	0	0
	0.487748	0	0	0			0.70802	1	0	1		0.543543	0	0	0
	0.489821	0	0	0			0.257875	0	1	1		0.471215	0	0	0
	0.765087	1	0	1			0.89593	1	1 Broken			0.090443	0	0	0
	0.270238	0	1	0			0.076973	0 Broken		0		0.844496	1	0	0
	0.102428	0	0	0			0.478412	0	0	0		0.189494	0	0	0
	0.780999	1	0	1			0.670554	0	0	0		0.116017	0	0	0
	0.782004	1	1 Broken				0.306271	0	0	0		0.185158	0	0	0
	0.543832	0 Broken		0			0.581487	0	0	0		0.366935	0	0	0
	0.983357	1	0	1			0.86435	1	0	1		0.66309	0	0	0
	0.724838	1	1 Broken				0.080347	0	1	1		0.951553	1	0	1
	0.62388	0 Broken		0			0.090044	0	1	0		0.996854	1	1	0
	0.336239	0	0	0			0.160622	0	0	0		0.128885	0	0	0
	0.458358	0	0	0			0.061522	0	0	0		0.971728	1	0	1
	0.643838	0	0	0			0.904577	1	0	1		0.405501	0	1	1

Figure 5. For “Fully Observable Three-component System” of state 3 (0, 1, 2)

4.2 Markov Chain Formulation

Markov chains are models used in the analysis of dynamical and stochastic systems, especially the study of the movement of systems between different states over time.

Additionally, the markov chain model is a mathematical model that represents the transition probabilities between certain states in your system. These states are the specific level of degradation of a component in the system.

Markovian Property

$$P \{ \text{future} \mid \text{present, past} \} = P \{ \text{future} \mid \text{present} \}$$

$$P \{ X_{t+1} = i_{t+1} \mid X_t = i_t, X_{t-1} = i_{t-1}, \dots, X_1 = i_1, X_0 = i_0 \} = P \{ X_{t+1} = i_{t+1} \mid X_t = i_t \}$$

$$X_t = S = \text{State Space}, \{X_0, X_1, X_2, \dots\}$$

The transition probabilities from each state to another determine future states depending on the current state of the system.

result of the relevant processes using Markov Process Properties are shown in the results and discussion. The vector $\pi = [\pi_0 \pi_1 \pi_2 \pi_3 \pi_4 \pi_5]$ is often called the steady-state distribution, or equilibrium distribution, for the Markov Chain. Steady-state probabilities can be used to describe the long-run behavior of a Markov Chain.

For single component systems, since we assumed there are 6 states (0 to 5) the component's states from 0 to 5 are "Normal" and when it reaches 5, it becomes "Broken". With alpha probability, it stays at the same state, with 1-alpha probability it updates to the next state. When it reaches K, in our case 5, it goes back to 0 with 1 probability. It goes into maintenance or parts are replaced and it returns to its normal state, back to state 0.

In the first part of the project, we defined 6 states for the single-component system. (0 to 5) We took the initial state where we started the Markov chain as 0, that is, a perfectly working system.

5. Results and Discussion

We first wrote the Markov Chain formulation to compare the distortion probabilities we obtained with the simulation method in Excel with Markov Chain. Then, we solved the equations by writing the matrices you see below. In order to compare the results we found regarding the probabilities of degradation and to test the accuracy of our simulation, we first ran and observed the simulation a thousand times. Then we recorded our observations by increasing the number of simulation runs to two thousand and then to four thousand.

5.1 Markov Chain Formulation and Relevant Calculations

State Space = $S = \{0,1,2,3,4,5\}$

State Distribution $\pi = [\pi_0 \pi_1 \pi_2 \pi_3 \pi_4 \pi_5]$

$$\pi \cdot P = \pi$$

$$[\pi_0 \pi_1 \pi_2 \pi_3 \pi_4 \pi_5] \cdot$$

$$[0.7 \ 0.3 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0.7 \ 0.3 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0.7 \ 0.3 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0.7 \ 0.3 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0.7 \ 0.3 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]$$

$$\pi_0 \cdot 0.7 + 1 \cdot \pi_5 = \pi_0 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad 0.3 \cdot \pi_0 = \pi_5$$

$$\pi_0 \cdot 0.3 + \pi_1 \cdot 0.7 = \pi_1 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \pi_0 = \pi_1$$

$$\pi_1 \cdot 0.3 + \pi_2 \cdot 0.7 = \pi_2 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \pi_1 = \pi_2$$

$$\pi_2 \cdot 0.3 + \pi_3 \cdot 0.7 = \pi_3 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \pi_2 = \pi_3$$

$$\pi_3 \cdot 0.3 + \pi_4 \cdot 0.7 = \pi_4 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \pi_3 = \pi_4$$

$$0.3 \cdot \pi_4 = \pi_5 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad 0.3 \cdot \pi_4 = \pi_5$$

$$\sum P_i = 1$$

$$\pi_0 + \pi_1 + \pi_2 + \pi_3 + \pi_4 + \pi_5 = 1$$

We solved this equation according to π_4 .

$$\pi_0 + \pi_1 + \pi_2 + \pi_3 + \pi_4 + \pi_5 = 1 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \pi_4 + \pi_4 + \pi_4 + \pi_4 + \pi_4 + 0.3 \cdot \pi_4 = 1$$

$$5.3 \cdot \pi_4 = 1 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \pi_4 = 0.188679 \sim 0.1887$$

$$5.3 \cdot \pi_4 = 1 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \pi_4 = 0.1887$$

$$\pi_0 = 0.1887$$

$$\pi_1 = 0.1887$$

$$\pi_2 = 0.1887$$

$$\pi_3 = 0.1887$$

$$\pi_5 = 0.0566$$

$$[\pi_0 \ \pi_1 \ \pi_2 \ \pi_3 \ \pi_4 \ \pi_5] \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad [0.1887 \ 0.1887 \ 0.1887 \ 0.1887 \ 0.1887 \ 0.0566]$$

The pi values found represent the degradation probabilities obtained in the long run.

In the single-component systems we simulated in Excel, we first obtained and compared the failure probabilities with 1000 simulations.

$$= [0.196 \ 0.161 \ 0.188 \ 0.227 \ 0.171 \ 0.057]$$

In the single-component systems we simulated in Excel, we later obtained and compared the failure probabilities with 2000 simulations.

$$= [0.19250 \ 0.1515 \ 0.1885 \ 0.2015 \ 0.208 \ 0.058]$$

Afterwards, we simulated 4000 times and observed the results.

$$= [0.1885 \ 0.18625 \ 0.18100 \ 0.19225 \ 0.19275 \ 0.05925]$$

5.2 The effect of changing the alpha value on the results

We also made changes to the parameters (changing the alpha values to 0.4 and 0.9) and observed how the results changed. It has been observed that as the alpha value increases, the probability of transition to the final state, that is, the degradation state, in the long run decreases.

i	0	1	2	3	4	broken
	740	687	684	723	739	427
	0.18500	0.17175	0.17100	0.18075	0.18475	0.10675

Figure 8. Results for alpha equals to 0.4 of one component

i	0	1	2	3	4	broken
	711	771	758	889	798	73
	0.17775	0.19275	0.18950	0.22225	0.19950	0.01825

Figure 9. Results for alpha equals to 0.9 of one component

In Figure 8, we changed the α value, which we took as 0.7 in the simulation we made in Excel, to 0.4. We observed that as the value of α decreases, it stays in the same state less often and moves to the next (updated) state more quickly. Therefore, we can comment that the degradation time of the system will be faster.

In Figure 9, we evaluated the results obtained in the simulation we conducted in Excel by increasing the α value to 0.9. As the α value increases, the probability of maintaining its state, that is, staying in the same state, increases, which shows that it reaches the decay state more slowly. That is, as the α value increases, the degradation of the components slows down. Therefore, the time required for corrective repair is prolonged. In short, as the value of α increases, the operating time of the intended states increases and the cost of the states per unit time decreases.

```
Probabilities
Probability 00 is 0.1467358497655381
Probability 01 is 0.1480007377344616
Probability 02 is 0.0884537041205245
Probability 10 is 0.1478490243739105
Probability 11 is 0.14912350809718913
Probability 12 is 0.08912473589361054
Probability 20 is 0.08834719114066958
Probability 21 is 0.0891087589466323
Probability 22 is 0.05325648992746372
```

Figure 10. Results for alpha equal to 0.4 of 2-components, 3-states (0,1,2)

In the simulation we made in Excel in Figure 10, we reduced the α value from 0.7 to 0.4. We observed that as the value of α decreases, it stays in the same state less often and moves to the next (updated) state more quickly. In other words, as the probability of components changing state increases, the probability of them being in the same state in future states also increases. Therefore, we can comment that the degradation time of the system will be faster.

```

Probabilities
Probability 00 is 0.23097084760469574
Probability 01 is 0.22651208268260098
Probability 02 is 0.022744250862807888
Probability 10 is 0.22692645836213707
Probability 11 is 0.22254576814545657
Probability 12 is 0.022345990197128428
Probability 20 is 0.0230643235926177
Probability 21 is 0.022619079536698516
Probability 22 is 0.0022711990158571444

```

Figure 11. Results for alpha equal to 0.9 of 2-components, 3-states (0,1,2)

As we see in Figure 11, according to the results we obtained from the simulation we conducted in Python by increasing the α value from 0.7 to 0.9, as the α value increases, the probability of being in the same state increases, which means that the degradation occurs more slowly. In other words, as the value of α gradually increases, the degradation of the components gradually decreases. Therefore, the time required for corrective repair is extended. Thus, it ensures that the operating time of the components increases and the costs per unit time of the states decrease, as we aim and desire.

```

Probabilities
Probability 000 is 0.05599975108476089
Probability 001 is 0.05643286094209319
Probability 002 is 0.03383670760408514
Probability 010 is 0.05643286094209319
Probability 011 is 0.056869320531252585
Probability 012 is 0.03409840540307746
Probability 020 is 0.03383670760408514
Probability 021 is 0.03409840540307746
Probability 022 is 0.02044514054627501
Probability 100 is 0.05682005004874889
Probability 101 is 0.05725950421226792
Probability 102 is 0.03433235652492381
Probability 110 is 0.05725950421226792
Probability 111 is 0.057702357175359785
Probability 112 is 0.03459788774155162
Probability 120 is 0.03433235652492381
Probability 121 is 0.03459788774155162
Probability 122 is 0.02074462629904762
Probability 200 is 0.033757159011851764
Probability 201 is 0.03401824157097666
Probability 202 is 0.020397074931632488
Probability 210 is 0.03401824157097666
Probability 211 is 0.03428134337889721
Probability 212 is 0.02055482874379255
Probability 220 is 0.020397074931632488
Probability 221 is 0.02055482874379255
Probability 222 is 0.012324516575004526

```

Figure 12. Results for alpha equal to 0.4 of 3-components, 3-states (0,1,2)

In the simulation we made in Excel in Figure 12, we reduced the α value from 0.7 to 0.4.

```

Probabilities
Probability 000 is 0.10913160220946716
Probability 001 is 0.10887956118024827
Probability 002 is 0.01081396639099233
Probability 010 is 0.10887956118024827
Probability 011 is 0.10862810224346754
Probability 012 is 0.010788991377669492
Probability 020 is 0.01081396639099233
Probability 021 is 0.01078899137766949
Probability 022 is 0.0010715674171176694
Probability 100 is 0.10758010045116775
Probability 101 is 0.10733164263792004
Probability 102 is 0.010660226433636882
Probability 110 is 0.10733164263792004
Probability 111 is 0.10708375864162085
Probability 112 is 0.010635606484990996
Probability 120 is 0.010660226433636882
Probability 121 is 0.010635606484990998
Probability 122 is 0.0010563331614288057
Probability 200 is 0.010742323115981613
Probability 201 is 0.010717513563848795
Probability 202 is 0.0010644682088918117
Probability 210 is 0.010717513563848795
Probability 211 is 0.010692761309738983
Probability 212 is 0.0010620098040163392
Probability 220 is 0.0010644682088918117
Probability 221 is 0.0010620098040163392
Probability 222 is 0.00010547928557982141
    
```

Figure 13. Results for alpha equal to 0.9 of 3-components, 3-states (0,1,2)

As we see in Figure 13, we increased the α value from 0.7 to 0.9.

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \pi_i \cdot c_i$$

We can adapt this formula, which can also be used for preventive maintenance, as follows to calculate the corrective maintenance cost that occurs when the system goes to corrective maintenance after the last failure occurs in the fully observable single-component systems we examined in the report:

$$E(\text{Cost}) = \pi_5 \cdot \$1000$$

$$E(\text{Cost}) = (0.0566) \cdot \$1000$$

$$=56.6$$

In the process shown above, the intervention to correct the malfunction was calculated assuming the corrective maintenance cost was \$1000.

As the cost of corrective maintenance increases, the importance of determining the optimal maintenance time and developing a preventive maintenance method that can be applied as the optimal maintenance method also increases.

To prevent costly malfunctions due to not being able to intervene until the moment of failure, the preventive maintenance intervention approach ensures the protection of the system and prolongs the operating time with early predictive interventions.

α	probability	value	cost(\$)
0.4	0,01825	18,25	1000
0.7	0,0566	56,6	
0.9	0,10675	106,75	

Figure 14. Chart for alpha – cost relationship

As you can see in Figure 14, as alpha increases, the final π_5 value (probability value for the degradation phase) increases, albeit slightly, and although the cost of maintenance seems to increase in the short term, when observed for a long time, the cost is actually expected to decrease, as we have explained before.

For multi-component systems, we first started with 2 component systems with 2 states. (0,1,2) If one component breaks, the system will crash even if the other component is working. We ran the simulations 10000 times. To find the long-run probabilities, first, we constructed a probability matrix. The alpha value we consider is 0.7, staying at the same state.

Fully Observable Two-component Systems

	0,0	1,0	2,0	0,1	1,1	2,1	0,2	1,2	2,2
0,0	α^2	$\alpha x(1-\alpha)$	0	$\alpha(1-\alpha)$	$(1-\alpha)^2$	0	0	0	0
1,0	0	α^2	$\alpha x(1-\alpha)$	0	$\alpha(1-\alpha)$	$(1-\alpha)^2$	0	0	0
2,0	α	0	0	$1-\alpha$	0	0	0	0	0
0,1	0	0	0	α^2	$\alpha x(1-\alpha)$	0	$\alpha(1-\alpha)$	$(1-\alpha)^2$	0
1,1	0	0	0	0	α^2	$\alpha x(1-\alpha)$	0	$\alpha(1-\alpha)$	$(1-\alpha)^2$
2,1	0	0	0	α	0	0	$(1-\alpha)$	0	0
0,2	α	$(1-\alpha)$	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1,2	0	α	$(1-\alpha)$	0	0	0	0	0	0
2,2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 15. Before constructing the matrix, the results we obtained are as follows above.

	0,0	1,0	2,0	0,1	1,1	2,1	0,2	1,2	2,2
0,0	0.49	0.21	0	0.21	0.09	0	0	0	0
1,0	0	0.49	0.21	0	0.21	0.09	0	0	0
2,0	0.7	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0
0,1	0	0	0	0.49	0.21	0	0.21	0.09	0
1,1	0	0	0	0	0.49	0.21	0	0.21	0.09
2,1	0	0	0	0.7	0	0	0.3	0	0
0,2	0.7	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1,2	0	0.7	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0
2,2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 16. After constructing the matrix, the results we obtained are as follows above.

The next step we had to do to find the probabilities was to find out how many times we stayed in states 0, 1, 2 in the simulation we ran 10000 times. We obtained these ratios by creating a pivot table in Excel. The results shown in the table were obtained in this way.

Sum of 1	Column Labels				
Row Labels	0	1	BOZULDI (blank)	Grand Total	
0	2759	1930	502	5191	
1	1953	1479	379	3811	
BOZULDU (blank)	567	340	92	999	
Grand Total	5279	3749	973	10001	
	0	1	boz		
0	0.27587241	0.19298	0.05019		
1	0.19528047	0.14789	0.0379		
boz	0.05669433	0.034	0.0092		

Figure 17. Pivot table of “Fully Observable Two-component System” of states 3 (0, 1, 2)

To find long-run probabilities, we wrote the ratios obtained from the simulation as a 1x9 matrix. Then, we multiplied it with the transition probability matrix using the MMULT formula in Excel.

[0.230021998	0.141708829	0.2510049	0.139568043	0.088389161	0.150144986	0.251694831	0.15370463	0.275872413]
--------------	-------------	-----------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	------------	--------------

Figure 18. Our calculations of the probabilities of being in states in a long run in a 2-component, 3-states system gave this result.

	Cost(\$)		first comp cost	scnd comp cost	Total Cost		
	0	pi0pi0	0	0	0	0.230022	pi0pi0
	0	pi1pi0	14.17088291	0	14.17088291	0.141709	pi1pi0
1st state	100	pi2pi0	125.5024498	0	125.5024498	0.251005	pi2pi0
2nd state	500	pi0pi1	0	13.95680432	13.95680432	0.139568	pi0pi1
		pi1pi1	8.838916108	8.838916108	17.67783222	0.088389	pi1pi1
		pi2pi1	75.07249275	15.01449855	90.0869913	0.150145	pi2pi1
		pi0pi2	0	125.8474153	125.8474153	0.251695	pi0pi2
		pi1pi2	15.37046295	76.85231477	92.22277772	0.153705	pi1pi2
		pi2pi2	137.9362064	137.9362064	275.8724128	0.275872	pi2pi2
					\$		
			376.8914109	378.4461554	755.3375662		

Figure 19. Cost Analysis of 2-components, 3-states system (0, 1, 2)

To calculate the total cost and to predict which state of deterioration we would require maintenance (optimal maintenance time), we first assigned cost parameters. In state 0, we set it as 0 because everything is in good condition and no maintenance will be required. In the intermediate states (states between 0 and the degradation state), we set the cost parameter to 100. In the last state, that is, the degradation state, we thought that there would be a further

increase in cost since correction would be made instead of maintenance, so we set the parameter to 500. We multiplied these parameters with the pi values, that is, the probabilities of disruption in the long run. For example, in the 2 component 3 state (0,1,2) system, we multiplied the pi1 value by 100 and the pi0 value by 0 to calculate the cost value incurred when the first component was in state 1 and the 2nd component was in state 0. We calculated the total cost by applying this to the whole system. We did the same method for different components and different states.

We set the deterioration cost of the components as \$100 in the first state and \$500 in the second state. The total cost is approximately \$755 with these cost parameters. The optimal cost is chosen approximately \$14 of deterioration probability ($\pi_0\pi_1$) in long-run simulation.

																1 step alp 2 step bet:3 step theta								
																α	α	0.25	0.1	0.05				
																	same state	0.6						
0,0	0,1	0,2	0,3	1,0	1,1	1,2	1,3	2,0	2,1	2,2	2,3	3,0	3,1	3,2	3,3									
0,0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0.03	0.15	0.0625	0.025	0.0125	0.06	0.025	0.01	0.005	0.03	0.0125	0.005	0.0025								
0,1	0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0	0.15	0.5	0.025	0	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0.03	0.0125	0.005								
0,2	0	0	0.36	0.15	0	0	0.15	0.0625	0	0	0.06	0.025	0	0	0.03	0.0125								
0,3	0.6	0	0	0	0.25	0	0	0	0.1	0	0	0	0.05	0	0	0								
1,0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0.03	0.15	0.0625	0.025	0.0125	0.06	0.025	0.01	0.005								
1,1	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0	0.15	0.0625	0.025	0	0.06	0.025	0.01								
1,2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0.15	0	0	0.15	0.0625	0	0	0.06	0.025								
1,3	0	0	0	0	0.6	0	0	0	0.25	0	0	0	0.1	0	0	0								
2,0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0.03	0.15	0.0625	0.025	0.0125								
2,1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0	0.15	0.0625	0.025								
2,2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0.15	0	0	0.15	0.0625								
2,3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.6	0	0	0	0.25	0	0	0								
3,0	0.6	0.25	0.1	0.05	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0								
3,1	0	0.6	0.25	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0								
3,2	0	0	0.6	0.25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0								
3,3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0								

Figure 20. Matrix of leaping states in 2-components, 4-states systems (0, 1, 2, 3)

We continued the same calculations in the 2-components 4-states (0, 1, 2, 3) system. But this time we discussed a leaping transition between states. With alpha probability, it can jump to the next state, and with beta, it can jump to the next two states, so it goes. In the 4-states system we are considering, it can jump from 0 to 3.

Sum of 1	Column Labels				
Row Labels	0	1	2 BOZULDU	Grand Total	
0	1359	1205	898	266	3728
1	1221	1105	785	209	3320
2	840	791	542	139	2312
BOZULDU	230	206	171	35	642
Grand Total	3650	3307	2396	649	10002
	0	1	2 bozulma		
0	0.135872825	0.12048	0.089782	0.026595	
1	0.122075585	0.11048	0.0784843	0.020896	
2	0.083983203	0.07908	0.0541892	0.013897	
bozulma	0.022995401	0.0206	0.0170966	0.003499	

Figure 21. Pivot table of “Fully Observable Two-component System” of states 4 (0, 1, 2, 3)

0.08217	0.0818586	0.076252	0.0322555	0.08351	0.08465	0.12925	0.032385273	0.072919416	0.07589457	0.0679	0.028715	0.03089	0.0321	0.02874	0.01216
---------	-----------	----------	-----------	---------	---------	---------	-------------	-------------	------------	--------	----------	---------	--------	---------	---------

Figure 22. After creating the transition probability matrix in the same way and multiplying it with the ratios we found in the simulation, we obtained the long-run probability matrix as shown above.

	COST(\$)	first comp cost	scnd comp cost	Total Cost		
	0	0	0	0	0.08217	pi0pi0
		0	0	0	0.08186	pi0pi1
1st state	100	0	8.185862827	8.18586283	0.07625	pi0pi2
2nd state	100	0	7.625174965	7.62517497	0.03226	pi0pi3
3rd state	500	0	16.12777445	16.1277744	0.08351	pi1pi0
		8.35142971	0	8.35142971	0.08465	pi1pi1
		8.46468206	8.464682064	16.9293641	0.12925	pi1pi2
		12.9252649	12.92526495	25.8505299	0.03239	pi1pi3
		3.23852729	16.19263647	19.4311638	0.07292	pi2pi0
		7.29194161	0	7.29194161	0.07589	pi2pi1
		7.58945711	7.589457109	15.1789142	0.0679	pi2pi2
		6.78966707	6.789667067	13.5793341	0.02871	pi2pi3
		2.8714757	14.35737852	17.2288542	0.03089	pi3pi0
		15.4459108	0	15.4459108	0.0321	pi3pi1
		16.0524145	3.210482903	19.2628974	0.02874	pi3pi2
		14.3706259	2.874125175	17.244751	0.01216	pi3pi3
		6.07765947	6.077659468	12.1553189		
				\$		
		109.469056	110.420166	219.889222		

Figure 23. Cost Analysis of 2-component, 4-state system (0, 1, 2, 3)

We made a cost calculation again by continuing the method we applied in the 2 component 3 state system. We set the deterioration cost of the components as \$100 in the first state, \$100 in the second state and \$500 in the third state. The total cost is approximately \$220 with these cost

We have manually analyzed the single-component systems we have discussed before. However, when we come to multi-component systems since there will be complexity in solving them manually, we solved it by using the relevant tools and performing the relevant operations in Excel to obtain the analytical solution.

Sum of x	Column Label			
Row Label	0	1 Broken	(blank)	Grand Total
0	3354	1887	489	5730
0	1922	1065	275	3262
1	1144	683	171	1998
Broken	288	139	43	470
1	1986	1169	279	3434
0	1146	674	159	1979
1	677	395	100	1172
Broken	163	100	20	283
Broken	474	287	75	836
0	273	163	44	480
1	171	110	24	305
Broken	30	14	7	51
(blank)				
(blank)				
Grand Total	5814	3343	843	10000
	0	1	2	
0,0	0.1922	0.1065	0.0275	
0,1	0.1144	0.0683	0.0171	
0,2	0.0288	0.0139	0.0043	
1,0	0.1146	0.0674	0.0159	
1,1	0.0677	0.0395	0.01	
1,2	0.0163	0.01	0.002	
2,0	0.0273	0.0163	0.0044	
2,1	0.0171	0.011	0.0024	
2,2	0.003	0.0014	0.0007	

Figure 27. Pivot table of “Fully Observable Three-component System” of states 3 (0, 1, 2) for 10000 runs

	000	001	002	010	011	012	020	021	022	100	101	102	110	111	112	120	121	122	200	201	202	210	211	212	220	221	222
000	0	0.49	0.147	0	0.147	0.063	0	0	0	0.147	0.063	0	0.063	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
001	0	0	0.49	0.147	0	0.147	0.063	0	0	0	0	0.147	0.063	0	0.063	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
002	0	0	0	0	0.21	0	0	0	0	0.21	0	0	0	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
010	0	0	0	0	0.49	0.147	0	0.147	0.063	0	0	0	0.147	0.063	0	0.063	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
011	0	0	0	0	0	0.49	0.147	0	0.147	0.063	0	0	0	0	0.147	0.063	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
012	0	0	0	0	0	0.49	0	0	0.09	0	0	0	0	0.21	0	0	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
020	0.49	0.21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.21	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
021	0	0.49	0.21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.21	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
022	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.49	0.147	0	0.147	0.063	0	0	0	0	0.147	0.063	0	0.063	0.09	0	0	0	0
101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.49	0.147	0	0.147	0.063	0	0	0	0.147	0.063	0	0.063	0.09	0	0	0	0
102	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.49	0	0	0.21	0	0	0	0	0	0.21	0	0	0.09	0	0	0	0	0
110	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.49	0.147	0	0	0	0	0.147	0.063	0	0	0.147	0.063	0.09	0	0
111	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.49	0.147	0	0.147	0.063	0	0	0	0	0.147	0.063	0.09	0	0.063
112	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.49	0	0	0	0.21	0	0	0	0	0	0.21	0	0	0.09	0
120	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.49	0.21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.21	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
121	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.49	0.21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.21	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0
122	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
200	0.49	0.21	0	0.21	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
201	0	0.49	0.21	0	0.21	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
202	0.7	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
210	0	0	0	0.49	0.21	0	0.21	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
211	0	0	0	0	0.49	0.21	0	0.21	0.09	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
212	0	0	0	0	0.7	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
220	0.7	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
221	0	0.7	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
222	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 28. Matrix of state in 3-components, 3-state system (0, 1, 2) for 10000 runs

0.12992	0.1155754	0.024719	0.114698	0.09325	0.020798	0.02225	0.0207	0.00517	0.1089	0.0929089	0.0211	0.0914703	0.0876893	0.0246705	0.02069	0.02463	0.00858	0.02242	0.02053	0.00529	0.01997	0.02394	0.00864	0.00515	0.00855	0.00356
---------	-----------	----------	----------	---------	----------	---------	--------	---------	--------	-----------	--------	-----------	-----------	-----------	---------	---------	---------	---------	---------	---------	---------	---------	---------	---------	---------	---------

Figure 29. Our calculations of the deterioration probabilities of being in states in a long run (10000) in a 3-components, 3-states (0,1,2) system provided us with this result.

	COST(\$)		1st comp cost	2nd comp cost	3rd comp cost	Total Cost		
0th state	0	000	0	0	0	0	pi0pi0pi0	0.12992
1st state	100	001	0	0	11.55754	11.55754	pi0pi0pi1	0.11558
2rd state	500	002	0	0	12.3594	12.3594	pi0pi0pi2	0.02472
		010	0	11.46984	0	11.46984	pi0pi1pi0	0.1147
		011	0	9.32496	9.32496	18.64992	pi0pi1pi1	0.09325
		012	0	2.07981	10.39905	12.47886	pi0pi1pi2	0.0208
		020	0	11.1261	0	11.1261	pi0pi2pi0	0.02225
		021	0	10.35135	2.07027	12.42162	pi0pi2pi1	0.0207
		022	0	2.58255	2.58255	5.1651	pi0pi2pi2	0.00517
		100	10.88974	0	0	10.88974	pi1pi0pi0	0.1089
		101	9.29089	0	9.29089	18.58178	pi1pi0pi1	0.09291
		102	2.10963	0	10.54815	12.65778	pi1pi0pi2	0.0211
		110	9.14703	9.14703	0	18.29406	pi1pi1pi0	0.09147
		111	8.76893	8.76893	8.76893	26.30679	pi1pi1pi1	0.08769
		112	2.46705	2.46705	12.33525	17.26935	pi1pi1pi2	0.02467
		120	2.06946	10.3473	0	12.41676	pi1pi2pi0	0.02069
		121	2.46318	12.3159	2.46318	17.24226	pi1pi2pi1	0.02463
		122	0.85815	4.29075	4.29075	9.43965	pi1pi2pi2	0.00858
		200	11.20875	0	0	11.20875	pi2pi0pi0	0.02242
		201	10.2633	0	2.05266	12.31596	pi2pi0pi1	0.02053
		202	2.64645	0	2.64645	5.2929	pi2pi0pi2	0.00529
		210	9.98415	1.99683	0	11.98098	pi2pi1pi0	0.01997
		211	11.9703	2.39406	2.39406	16.75842	pi2pi1pi1	0.02394
		212	4.31775	0.86355	4.31775	9.49905	pi2pi1pi2	0.00864
		220	2.5731	2.5731	0	5.1462	pi2pi2pi0	0.00515
		221	4.27725	4.27725	0.85545	9.40995	pi2pi2pi1	0.00855
		222	1.7775	1.7775	1.7775	5.3325	pi2pi2pi2	0.00356
		TOTAL	107.08261	108.15386	110.03479	325.2713		

Figure 30. Cost Analysis of 3-components, 3-states system (0, 1, 2) for 10000 runs

We set the deterioration cost of the components as \$100 in the first state and \$500 in the second state. The total cost is approximately \$325 with these cost parameters. The optimal cost is chosen approximately \$5 of deterioration probability (pi2pi2pi0) in long-run simulation.

Sum of x	Column								
Row Label	0	1	Broken	(blank)	Grand Total				
0	3254	2018	453		5725				
0	1805	1112	257		3174				
1	1171	741	161		2073				
Broken	278	165	35		478				
1	1991	1190	286		3467				
0	1109	681	161		1951		0	1	2
1	712	407	111		1230	0,0	0.1805	0.1112	0.0257
Broken	170	102	14		286	0,1	0.1171	0.0741	0.0161
Broken	464	286	58		808	0,2	0.0278	0.0165	0.0035
0	279	168	33		480	1,0	0.1109	0.0681	0.0161
1	154	100	16		270	1,1	0.0712	0.0407	0.0111
Broken	31	18	9		58	1,2	0.017	0.0102	0.0014
(blank)						2,0	0.0279	0.0168	0.0033
(blank)						2,1	0.0154	0.01	0.0016
Grand Total	5709	3494	797		10000	2,2	0.0031	0.0018	0.0009

Figure 31. Pivot table of “Fully Observable Three-component System” of states 3 (0, 1, 2) for leaping transitions

0,0	0,1	0,2	1,0	1,1	1,2	2,0	2,1	2,2	0,0	0,1	0,2	1,0	1,1	1,2	2,0	2,1	2,2	0,0	0,1	0,2	1,0	1,1	1,2	2,0	2,1	2,2	
0,0	0.216	0.09	0.036	0.09	0.0375	0.015	0.036	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	
0,1	0	0.216	0.09	0	0.09	0.0375	0	0.036	0.015	0	0.09	0.0375	0	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	
0,2	0.36	0	0	0.15	0	0	0.06	0	0	0.15	0	0.0625	0	0.025	0	0	0.06	0	0.025	0	0.01	0	0	0.01	0	0	
1,0	0	0	0	0.216	0.09	0.036	0.09	0.0375	0.015	0.036	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.036	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	
1,1	0	0	0	0	0.216	0.09	0	0	0.09	0.0375	0	0	0.09	0.0375	0	0.0375	0.015	0	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	
1,2	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0	0	0.15	0	0	0.0625	0	0	0.025	0	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
2,0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0	0	0	0	0	0.15	0.0625	0.025	0	0	0	0	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
2,1	0	0.36	0.15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.15	0.0625	0	0	0	0	0.06	0.025	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
2,2	0.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
0,0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.216	0.09	0.036	0.09	0.0375	0.015	0.036	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.036	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	
0,1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.216	0.09	0	0.09	0.0375	0	0.036	0.015	0	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	
0,2	0.36	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0	0.15	0	0	0.0625	0	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
1,0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.216	0.09	0.036	0.09	0.0375	0.015	0.036	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.036	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	
1,1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.216	0.09	0	0.09	0.0375	0	0.036	0.015	0	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	
1,2	0.36	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0	0.15	0	0	0.0625	0	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
2,0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0	0	0.0625	0.025	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
2,1	0	0.36	0.15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0.15	0	0	0.0625	0.025	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
2,2	0.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.6	0	0.36	0.15	0	0	0.0625	0.15	0.0625	0.025	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
0,0	0.216	0.09	0.036	0.09	0.0375	0.015	0.036	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	
0,1	0	0.216	0.09	0	0.09	0.0375	0	0.036	0.015	0	0.09	0.0375	0	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	
0,2	0.36	0	0	0.15	0	0	0.06	0	0	0.15	0	0.0625	0	0.025	0	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
1,0	0	0	0	0.216	0.09	0.036	0.09	0.0375	0.015	0.036	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.036	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	
1,1	0	0	0	0	0.216	0.09	0	0	0.09	0.0375	0	0	0.09	0.0375	0	0.0375	0.015	0	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	0.0375	0.015	
1,2	0.36	0	0	0	0	0.36	0	0	0.15	0	0	0.0625	0	0	0.025	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
2,0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0.15	0.06	0	0	0.0625	0.025	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
2,1	0	0.36	0.15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.36	0.15	0	0	0.0625	0.025	0.06	0.025	0.01	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
2,2	0.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.6	0	0.36	0.15	0	0	0.0625	0.15	0.0625	0.025	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
0,0	0.1805	0.1112	0.0257	0.1171	0.0741	0.0161	0.0278	0.0185	0.0035	0.1109	0.0681	0.0161	0.0712	0.0407	0.0111	0.017	0.0102	0.0014	0.0279	0.0168	0.0033	0.0154	0.01	0.0016	0.0031	0.0018	0.0009

Figure 32. Matrix of state in 3-components, 3-state system (0, 1, 2) for leaping transitions

[0.076131 0.0665 0.0298 0.0667 0.06058 0.0267147 0.0299548 0.0268859 0.012 0.0668844 0.0601 0.026 0.0619 0.055 0.025 0.0303 0.0265 0.0098 0.0367 0.0323 0.0148 0.0329 0.0287 0.0134 0.0165 0.014 0.0415]

Figure 33. Our calculations of the deterioration probabilities of being in leaping transitions in a long run in a 3-components, 3-states (0,1,2) system provided us with this result.

			1st comp cost	2nd comp cost	3rd comp cost	Total Cost		
		000	0	0	0	0	pi0pi0pi0	0.07613
	COST(\$)	001	0	0	6.65452	6.65452	pi0pi0pi1	0.06655
0th state	0	002	0	0	14.9138	14.9138	pi0pi0pi2	0.02983
1st state	100	010	0	6.67236	0	6.67236	pi0pi1pi0	0.06672
2rd state	500	011	0	6.058275	6.058275	12.11655	pi0pi1pi1	0.06058
		012	0	2.67147	13.35735	16.02882	pi0pi1pi2	0.02671
		020	0	14.9774	0	14.9774	pi0pi2pi0	0.02995
		021	0	13.4297	2.68594	16.11564	pi0pi2pi1	0.02686
		022	0	6.0604	6.0604	12.1208	pi0pi2pi2	0.01212
		100	6.68844	0	0	6.68844	pi1pi0pi0	0.06688
		101	6.01374	0	6.01374	12.02748	pi1pi0pi1	0.06014
		102	2.5974	0	12.987	15.5844	pi1pi0pi2	0.02597
		110	6.18552	6.18552	0	12.37104	pi1pi1pi0	0.06186
		111	5.50287	5.50287	5.50287	16.50861	pi1pi1pi1	0.05503
		112	2.50335	2.50335	12.51675	17.52345	pi1pi1pi2	0.02503
		120	3.02814	15.1407	0	18.16884	pi1pi2pi0	0.03028
		121	2.6478	13.239	2.6478	18.5346	pi1pi2pi1	0.02648
		122	0.9842475	4.9212375	4.9212375	10.8267225	pi1pi2pi2	0.00984
		200	18.3518	0	0	18.3518	pi2pi0pi0	0.0367
		201	16.13245	0	3.22649	19.35894	pi2pi0pi1	0.03226
		202	7.40645	0	7.40645	14.8129	pi2pi0pi2	0.01481
		210	16.4511	3.29022	0	19.74132	pi2pi1pi0	0.0329
		211	14.342625	2.868525	2.868525	20.079675	pi2pi1pi1	0.02869
		212	6.683925	1.336785	6.683925	14.704635	pi2pi1pi2	0.01337
		220	8.255275	8.255275	0	16.51055	pi2pi2pi0	0.01651
		221	6.996525	6.996525	1.399305	15.392355	pi2pi2pi1	0.01399
		222	20.7346438	20.73464375	20.7346438	62.20393125	pi2pi2pi2	0.04147
		TOTAL	151.506301	140.8442563	136.639021	428.9895788		

Figure 34. Cost Analysis of 3-components, 3-states system (0, 1, 2) with leaping transitions

We set the deterioration cost of the components as \$100 in the first state and \$500 in the second state. The total cost is approximately \$429 with these cost parameters. The optimal cost is chosen approximately \$7 of deterioration probability (pi0pi0pi1) in long run simulation.

By performing cost analysis in this way (as clearly explained in 2 component 3 states part), we found the optimal result in different deterioration situations in 2 and 3 component systems. It should not be ignored that the lowest cost may change in different states due to different cost parameters (by obtaining information from real life, companies).

5.3 Validation with Python

We performed a validation process by coding our system in Python. There are two codes for validation. First code is for single-component systems. Second code is for multi-component systems with or without leap probability.

Firstly, for a single-component system we required the number of states, number of simulations and alpha number from the receiver as input. Then, in the first simulation, when it reached the state that was the deterioration level, the system continued to process by restarting

the system. When the desired simulation result was achieved, we recorded all “stayed” movements (how many times it stayed at current state) with a counter. With another counter, we collected the number of times each state remained in itself in each simulation. We did not include the state with the distortion level in the probability calculation because it would reach the state with the distortion level in any case for the completion of the simulation. When we divided this data into all movements for each state one by one, we wrote an output that gave the probability of the system remaining in itself in each state. As can be seen from the results obtained from other calculations; The probabilities approached each other as the number of simulations increased.

Secondly, We required input from the user on the number of components, deterioration level for each component, alpha number and beta (leap probability) number. There, unlike the previous code, instead of running the simulation for a specific number of times and observing it until it breaks, we took a specific number of movements and observed it. After taking as many movements as desired and recording all movements, we created a counter that counts how long each component remained in which state. Again, unlike the other code, all states, including the deterioration state, were printed in the output of this code. The reason why we printed the deterioration state was to be able to compare all probabilities with each other more easily and get a clearer result in more complex and large studies such as multi-component systems instead of single-component systems. A separate probability calculation was made for each component and state with the data collected in the other counter. We multiplied the separately calculated probabilities with each other and wrote them in order to create final probabilities.

Below are the outputs of the validation made with various values.

1. Fully Observable Two-component Systems

```
Probabilities
Probability 00 is 0.1894123983447098
Probability 01 is 0.18986710782171332
Probability 02 is 0.057558161646016105
Probability 10 is 0.18794447756651722
Probability 11 is 0.18839566310583153
Probability 12 is 0.057112093584088135
Probability 20 is 0.05624217540967687
Probability 21 is 0.056377192179379206
Probability 22 is 0.017090730342067848
```

Figure 35. Python output for 2-components, 3 states (0, 1, 2) system (alpha=0.7, beta=0)

2. Fully Observable Three-component Systems

```
Probabilities
Probability 000 is 0.08264676877479717
Probability 001 is 0.08178152536381636
Probability 002 is 0.024650809429652868
Probability 010 is 0.08178152536381636
Probability 011 is 0.08092534033674269
Probability 012 is 0.02439273581406519
Probability 020 is 0.024650809429652868
Probability 021 is 0.02439273581406519
Probability 022 is 0.007352524660617672
Probability 100 is 0.08338017186556632
Probability 101 is 0.08250725032994387
Probability 102 is 0.02486955941944293
Probability 110 is 0.08250725032994388
Probability 111 is 0.08164346756185219
Probability 112 is 0.0246091956721281
Probability 120 is 0.02486955941944293
Probability 121 is 0.024609195672128097
Probability 122 is 0.007417770578770224
Probability 200 is 0.02503082221055096
Probability 201 is 0.02476877017500041
Probability 202 is 0.007465869958705211
Probability 210 is 0.02476877017500041
Probability 211 is 0.024509461607832902
Probability 212 is 0.007387708466310857
Probability 220 is 0.007465869958705211
Probability 221 is 0.007387708466310857
Probability 222 is 0.0022268231451383095
```

Figure 36. Python output for 3-components, 3 states (0, 1, 2) system ($\alpha=0.7$, $\beta=0$)

3. Fully Observable Three-component Systems with Leap

```
Probabilities
Probability 000 is 0.08526103099975879
Probability 001 is 0.0708497539309077
Probability 002 is 0.038208097536807796
Probability 010 is 0.0708497539309077
Probability 011 is 0.05887434825980901
Probability 012 is 0.03174995982230863
Probability 020 is 0.03820809753680779
Probability 021 is 0.03174995982230863
Probability 022 is 0.017122226886821808
Probability 100 is 0.07004720859517909
Probability 101 is 0.05820745344411142
Probability 102 is 0.031390314505970435
Probability 110 is 0.05820745344411143
Probability 111 is 0.04836891725449259
Probability 112 is 0.026084555071449935
Probability 120 is 0.031390314505970435
Probability 121 is 0.02608455507144993
Probability 122 is 0.014066968042628808
Probability 200 is 0.03720967629928387
Probability 201 is 0.03092029710103375
Probability 202 is 0.01667480353785665
Probability 210 is 0.030920297101033747
Probability 211 is 0.025693982530952474
Probability 212 is 0.013856338747612785
Probability 220 is 0.01667480353785665
Probability 221 is 0.013856338747612787
Probability 222 is 0.007472493734955386
```

Figure 37. Python output for 3-components, 3 states (0, 1, 2) system ($\alpha=0.6$, $\beta=0.1$)

5.4 Validation with MINITAB

A paired t test is used to determine whether the mean difference between two data sets is significantly different. In this study, we tested whether data sets taken from two different methods (Excel and Python) to be compared using the paired t-test give similar results. In our research, we used data sets from three different situations in nature (2 component 3 situations, 3 component 3 situations, and 3 component 3 situations with jump probability) and evaluated the reliability of these data sets. This comparison is critical to check the reliability and validity of data obtained from different methods.

Hypothesis Testing of 2-components, 3-states in Minitab for Validation

Figure 38. Paired T-Test for 2-components, 3-states (0, 1, 2)

Descriptive Statistics:

Sample Size (N): 9

Mean: excel: 0.1111, python: 0.1111

Standard Deviations (StDev): 0.0753, 0.0750, respectively.

Standard Error of the Mean (SE Mean):0.0251, 0.0250

The means of both samples are identical.

Estimation for Paired Difference:

Mean Difference: 0.000000

Standard Deviation of the Differences (StDev): 0.001287

Standard Error of the Mean Difference (SE Mean): 0.000429

95% Confidence Interval for the Mean Difference: (-0.000989, 0.000989)

Null hypothesis ($H_0: \mu_{\text{difference}} = 0$), that is, the hypothesis that the difference is zero.

Alternative hypothesis ($H_1: \mu_{\text{difference}} \neq 0$), i.e. the hypothesis that the difference is non-zero.

T-Value: -0.00

P-Value: 1.000

The t-value is 0, and the p-value is 1.000, which is higher than the alpha level of 0.05. This confirms that there is no statistically significant difference between the two.

Figure 39. Histogram Chart and Plot Chart of Differences for 2-components, 3-states (0, 1, 2)

Figure 40. Boxplot Chart of Differences for 2-components, 3-states (0, 1, 2)

Histogram of Differences:

The histogram in Figure 39 is symmetrical and centered, suggesting a nearly normal distribution.

Individual Value Plot of Differences:

Dots represent each difference. Most differences cluster around 0. Both the null hypothesis (H_0) and the 95% confidence interval are centered around 0, meaning that there is no significant difference.

Boxplot of Differences:

The boxplot demonstrates the data's central tendency and distribution. The median difference is near zero. The box's width shows the spread of data, with a symmetrical distribution around 0. The differences fall within a narrow range, with lower and upper quartiles between -0.001 and 0.001. The confidence interval is also tight around zero.

These graphs show that the differences between the two groups are statistically insignificant and small. The central tendencies and distributions of the data support the conclusion that there is no significant difference.

Hypothesis Testing of 3-components, 3-states in Minitab for Validation

WORKSHEET 1

Paired T-Test and CI: 3c2staexc, 3s2stapy

Descriptive Statistics

Sample	N	Mean	StDev	SE Mean
3c2staexc	27	0.04216	0.04168	0.00802
3s2stapy	27	0.03704	0.03087	0.00594

Estimation for Paired Difference

Mean	StDev	SE Mean	95% CI for $\mu_{\text{difference}}$
0.00512	0.01310	0.00252	(-0.00006, 0.01030)

$\mu_{\text{difference}}$: population mean of (3c2staexc - 3s2stapy)

Test

Null hypothesis $H_0: \mu_{\text{difference}} = 0$
Alternative hypothesis $H_1: \mu_{\text{difference}} \neq 0$

T-Value	P-Value
2.03	0.052

Figure 41. Paired T-Test for 3-components, 3-states (0,1,2)

Descriptive statistics:

Sample Size (N): 27

Mean: excel: 0.04216, python: 0.03704

Standard Deviations (StDev): 0.04168, 0.03087, respectively.

Standard Error of the Mean (SE Mean): 0.00802, 0.00594

Estimation for Paired Difference:

Mean Difference: 0.00512

Standard Deviation of the Differences (StDev): 0.01310

Standard Error of the Mean Difference (SE Mean): 0.00252

95% Confidence Interval for the Mean Difference: (-0.00006, 0.01030)

Null hypothesis ($H_0: \mu_{\text{difference}} = 0$), that is, the hypothesis that the difference is zero.

Alternative hypothesis ($H_1: \mu_{\text{difference}} \neq 0$), i.e. the hypothesis that the difference is non-zero.

T-Value: -0.00

P-Value: 1.000

The t-value is 2.03 and the p value is 0.052. The T value is positive at 2.03, indicating that there is some difference between the means, but this difference is not statistically significant. Since the P value is greater than 0.05, we cannot reject the null hypothesis. This shows that there is no significant difference between the two samples.

Figure 42. Histogram Chart and Plot Chart of Differences for 3-components, 3-states (0, 1, 2)

Figure 43. Boxplot Chart of Differences for 3-components, 3-states (0, 1, 2)

Histogram of Differences:

Distribution of Frequencies: The histogram displays the distribution of the differences. Variations are centered in the range of 0.000 and 0.012.

The Confidence Interval and Mean: The null hypothesis (H_0) mean and the 95% confidence interval (CI) of the differences (\bar{X}) mean are displayed on the histogram by the red dot and line. The mean's confidence interval (\bar{X}) lies between 0.00006 and 0.01030.

Individual Value Plot of Differences:

The histogram shows that the majority of the differences are near zero, indicating that there is typically little difference between the two groups. The graph's red dot and line represent the mean of the deviations from the null hypothesis, as well as its 95% confidence interval. The confidence interval and the mean difference are almost equal, so the majority of the differences can be neglected.

Boxplot of Differences:

A box plot displays the distribution of differences. The upper/lower quartiles and median are included in the box. The mean of the deviations from the null hypothesis, as well as its 95% confidence interval, are displayed by the red dot and line. This suggests that the average difference is not significant and is near to zero.

The graph's mean difference and 95% confidence interval are quite near to zero, and since 0 is included in the confidence interval, two groups' differences are not statistically significant. A few outliers exist, but the majority of the data is very close to zero.

The 95% confidence level indicates that there is no significant difference, by the P-value of 0.052.

Hypothesis Testing of 3-components, 3-states (with leaping transitions) in Minitab for Validation

Figure 44. Paired T-Test for 3-components, 3-states (0,1,2) with leaping transitions

Descriptive statistics:

Sample Size (N): 27

Mean: excel: 0.03658, python: 0.03704

Standard Deviations (StDev): 0.02002, 0.02079, respectively.

Standard Error of the Mean (SE Mean):0.00385 0.0400

Estimation for Paired Difference:

Mean Difference: -0.00046

Standard Deviation of the Differences (StDev): 0.00770

Standard Error of the Mean Difference (SE Mean): 0.00148

95% Confidence Interval for the Mean Difference: (-0.00350, 0.00259)

Null hypothesis ($H_0: \mu_{\text{difference}} = 0$), that is, the hypothesis that the difference is zero.

Alternative hypothesis ($H_1: \mu_{\text{difference}} \neq 0$), i.e. the hypothesis that the difference is non-zero.

T-Value: -0.31

P-Value: 0.761

We cannot reject the H_0 hypothesis as this value is greater than 0.05, meaning the difference between groups is not significant.

Figure 45. Histogram Chart and Plot Chart of Differences for 3-components, 3-states (0, 1, 2) with leaping transitions

Figure 46. Boxplot Chart of Differences for 3-components, 3-states (0, 1, 2) with leaping transitions

Histogram of Differences:

The distribution of differences is displayed in the histogram. (close to zero)

Individual Value Plot of Differences:

The confidence interval includes zero and the majority of values are centered around 0.

Boxplot of Differences:

The distribution and median of the differences are shown in the box plot. The confidence interval includes zero and the median is also close to zero.

According to these graphs and paired t-test results, we accept the H_0 hypothesis and declare that there is no significant difference between the two data sets because the P value is greater than 0.05.

6. Conclusions

In summary, this project underlines the important role of industrial maintenance planning in reducing risks and optimizing efficiency, reliability, and cost-effectiveness. The research is driven by the need for effective maintenance in industries that rely on reliable system performance.

In the thesis, we initially focused on single-component fully observable systems using simulation and Markov Chain formulation to predict degradation probabilities. Then we focused on multi-component fully observable systems. Afterwards, we examined the degradation of components in multi-component systems in skip steps rather than step by step.

In the methodology, a Markov Chain was developed to verify the simulation results. The steady state of the Markov Chain was compared with simulation results from various runs, revealing consistent degradation probabilities. In the project, we handled alpha, beta, number of components, number of states and costs parametrically. In this way, we have made the solution system we use easily adaptable in order to obtain results for different cases.

Validation using Python code further confirmed the reliability of the simulation approach; the fact that the code went consistently with both simulation and Markov chain-derived probabilities increased confidence in the results.

Another case in the project is to create a conditional maintenance strategy for systems that fail in environments where the probability of deterioration of operational factors is partially observable, and information about the time to go to maintenance is provided through colored sensors (green; "good", yellow; "starting to deteriorate", red; "broken"). Decisions can be made whether it should be serviced or parts replaced. Thus, this strategy can be further applied to larger and more complex structures for optimal maintenance process management. Machine learning and reinforcement learning, which aim to continuously learn from system behavior and changing conditions to maximize the sensitivity and accuracy of the algorithm, can be used for the continuation of the project. In addition, if the solution time increases and computational complexity is encountered in multi-component systems of the project, the search focus can be directed to different intelligent search algorithms. It will be possible to obtain simulations in a shorter time with code written using smart searches.

7. References

- [1] Flory J. A., Kharoufeh J.P., Abdul-Malak D.T. Optimal replacement of continuously degrading systems in partially observed environments.
- [2] Jin L., Yamamoto W. Optimal inspection policy for scheduled maintenance of aging systems. *Int J Ind Eng* 2017;24(4):420-21
- [3] de Jongea B., Scarf P. A. A review on maintenance optimization
- [4] A. Almakhlafi, J. Knowles Benchmarks for maintenance scheduling problems in power generation 2012 IEEE Congr. Evol. Comput. CEC 2012 (2012), pp. 10-15, 10.1109/CEC.2012.6252988
- Karabag, O., A. S. Eruguz, and R. Basten (2020). Integrated optimization of maintenance interventions and spare part selection for a partially observable multi-component system. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety* 200, 106955
- Karabag O., Bulut O., Toy A.O., Fadiloglu M.M An Efficient Procedure for Optimal Maintenance Intervention in Partially Observable Multi-Component Systems
- Karabag O., Toy A.O. (2022) Markovian Decision Process Modeling Approach for Intervention Planning of Partially Observable Systems Prone to Failures
- Cheng, W. and X. Zhao (2023). Maintenance optimization for dependent two-component degrading systems subject to imperfect repair. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety* 240, 109581
- Hao, Y., X. Zhu, and W. Kuo (2023). Optimization of condition-based maintenance with multiple times of component reallocation using Markov decision process. *IEEE Transactions on Reliability*, 1–11.
- Shi, Y., W. Zhu, Y. Xiang, and Q. Feng (2020). Condition-based maintenance optimization for multi-component systems subject to a system reliability requirement. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety* 202, 107042
- Vormdal A., (2020) Maintenance Optimization by Use of a Markov Model, A Steam Trap Case Study Using Empirical Plant Data

Çekyay B., Özekici S., (2012) Optimal maintenance of systems with Markovian mission and deterioration, Volume 219, Issue 1

Ross S. M. (2011) Introduction to Probability Models. 11th Ed., Academic Press, Ltd., 191-195

Winston W. L. (2004) Operations Research: Applications and Algorithms. 4th Edition, Brooks/Cole 923-939

Frederick S. Hillier, Gerald J. Lieberman (2010) Introduction to Operations Research, 10th Edition, MCGraw-Hill 905-908

Garcia, P., & Torres, M. (2019). Maintenance scheduling in the automotive industry. *Industrial Maintenance Journal*.

Huang, L., & Zhang, X. (2018). Comparison of Excel and Python in simulation-based maintenance optimization. *Computational Maintenance Review*.

Jones, T., & Brown, L. (2016). Simulation and Markov Decision Processes for multi-component systems. *Maintenance Management Quarterly*.

Lee, H., & Kim, J. (2017). Advanced simulation techniques for maintenance optimization using Python. *Journal of Applied Maintenance Engineering*.

Muller, A., Crespo Marquez, A., & Iung, B. (2017). Maintenance management in the context of complex systems. *Engineering Asset Management Review*.

Smith, R., & Taylor, P. (2015). Excel-based simulation for maintenance optimization. *Operations Research Letters*.

Thompson, D., Wilson, J., & Roberts, M. (2020). Optimizing medical equipment maintenance. *Healthcare Technology Review*.

Zhao, R., Xie, M., & Tang, Y. (2014). Statistical hypothesis testing in maintenance simulations. *Journal of Statistical Software*.

8. Appendix

Python Code for single-component system

```
import numpy as np
import random

break_loop_repeat_count = True

print("please enter the number of simulation:")
loop_count = int(input())

print("please enter deterioration level:")
k_states_list = int(input())

how_many_times = 5

while (True):
    print("please enter the 'alpha' number:")
    alpha = float(input())
    if alpha > 1.0 or alpha < 0.0:
        print("please write a number between 0.0 and 1.0")
    else:
        break

main_list = []
print("\nthe k_states starts:")
count_global = 0
for loop in range(loop_count):
    print("Simulation" , (loop+1) , "starts")
    NumberOfState = 0
    state_count_list = []
    for i in range(k_states_list):
        if k_states_list == i + 1:
            print(" you have reached the deterioration level ")
            break

    break_the_loop = False
    i_prob = np.array([alpha,1-alpha])
    NumberOfState = NumberOfState + 1
    prob_count = 0
    count_state = 0

    while break_loop_repeat_count:

        state_list = ["self_state","next_state"]

        choice = np.random.choice(state_list,replace=True,
p=i_prob)

        count_state = count_state + 1
        if choice == "next_state":
            print("state",NumberOfState,": It moved to the next
state")
```

```

        state_count_list.append(count_state)
        break
    else:
        print("state",NumberOfState,": it stayed at the
current state")
        main_list.append(state_count_list)

index = 0
state_count_sum = []
for j in range(k_states_list -1):
    variable = 0
    for i in main_list:
        variable = variable + i[j]
    state_count_sum.append(variable)

count_global = sum(state_count_sum)

for i in range(len(state_count_sum)):
    print("the state", (i+1), "'s probability is =
", (state_count_sum[i]/count_global))

```

Python Code for multi-component system

```

import numpy as np

import random

def machine_work(k_states_list,alpha,beta, break_loop_repeat_count =
True, main_list_func = []):

    NumberOfState = 0

    state_count_list = []

    state_count_list.append(1)

    c= 0

    for i in range(k_states_list):

        if k_states_list == i + 1:

            print( " component reached the deterioration level ")

            break

```

```

i_prob = np.array([alpha,1-(alpha + beta),beta])

NumberOfState = NumberOfState + 1

while break_loop_repeat_count:

    state_list = ["self_state","next_state","leap_state"]

    choice = np.random.choice(state_list,replace=True,
p=i_prob)

    c=c+1

    if choice == "leap_state":

        if (NumberOfState + 2) > k_states_list:

            print("state",NumberOfState,": component moved
to the next state")

            state_count_list.append(NumberOfState+1)

            print("current state: State",NumberOfState + 1)

            break

        else:

            print("state",NumberOfState,": component moved
to the next state")

            state_count_list.append(NumberOfState+2)

            print("current state: State",NumberOfState + 2)

            if c == 100 :

                print('component reached the 100th step')

                break

```

```

        elif choice == "next_state":

            print("state",NumberOfState,": component moved to
the next state")

            state_count_list.append(NumberOfState+1)

            print("current state: State",NumberOfState + 1)

            break

        else:

            print("state",NumberOfState,": component stayed at
the current state")

            print("current state: State",NumberOfState)

            state_count_list.append(NumberOfState)

            if c == 100 :

                print('component reached the 100th step')

                break

    return state_count_list

k_states_list= []

print("how many component will we use (must be 2 or 3):")

machine_count = int(input())

for i in range (machine_count):

    print("please enter deterioration level for component ", i+1,"
:")

    k_states_list.append(int(input())+1)

while (True):

    print("please enter the 'alpha' number:")

    alpha = float(input())

```

```

print("please enter the 'beta' (leap probability) number:")

beta = float(input())

if (alpha > 1.0 or alpha < 0.0) or ((beta > 1.0 or beta < 0.0)
and (alpha > beta and ((alpha + beta) < 1 ))):

    print("please write a number between 0.0 and 1.0")

else:

    break

def list_compare(list1,list2,list3 = []):

    list1_states_results = []

    list2_states_results = []

    list3_states_results = []

    if len(list3) == 0:

        min_len = min(len(list1),len(list2))

        if len(list1) == len(list2):

            for num in range(k_states_list[0]):

                num_count_list1 = [state for state in list1 if
state==(num+1)]

list1_states_results.append(len(num_count_list1)/len(list1))

                for num in range(k_states_list[1]):

                    num_count_list2 = [state for state in list2 if
state==(num+1)]

list2_states_results.append(len(num_count_list2)/len(list2))

            else:

```

```

        for num in range(k_states_list[0]):
            num_count_list1 = [state for state in
list1[0:min_len+1] if state==(num+1)]

list1_states_results.append(len(num_count_list1)/(min_len+1))

        for num in range(k_states_list[1]):
            num_count_list2 = [state for state in
list2[0:min_len+1] if state==(num+1)]

list2_states_results.append(len(num_count_list2)/(min_len+1))

        print("One of the components already reached the
deterioration level. ")

    else:
        min_len = min(len(list1),len(list2),len(list3))

        if len(list1) == len(list2) == len(list3):
            for num in range(k_states_list[0]):
                num_count_list1 = [state for state in list1 if
state==(num+1)]

list1_states_results.append(len(num_count_list1)/len(list1))

                for num in range(k_states_list[1]):
                    num_count_list2 = [state for state in list2 if
state==(num+1)]

list2_states_results.append(len(num_count_list2)/len(list2))

            for num in range(k_states_list[2]):

```

```

        num_count_list3 = [state for state in list3 if
state==(num+1)]

list3_states_results.append(len(num_count_list3)/len(list3))

    else:

        for num in range(k_states_list[0]):

            num_count_list1 = [state for state in
list1[0:min_len+1] if state==(num+1)]

list1_states_results.append(len(num_count_list1)/(min_len+1))

            for num in range(k_states_list[1]):

                num_count_list2 = [state for state in
list2[0:min_len+1] if state==(num+1)]

list2_states_results.append(len(num_count_list2)/(min_len+1))

                for num in range(k_states_list[2]):

                    num_count_list3 = [state for state in
list3[0:min_len+1] if state==(num+1)]

list3_states_results.append(len(num_count_list3)/(min_len+1))

            print("One of the components already reached the
deterioration level. ")

    return list1_states_results,list2_states_results

print("\nthe k_states starts:")

count_global = 0

```

```

machine_broken = True

compstatlist1 = []
compstatlist2 = []
compstatlist3 = []

counter = 0

while (machine_broken):

    print("Component 1" , "starts")

    print("number of states", k_states_list[0])

    main_list_makine1 = machine_work(k_states_list =
k_states_list[0],alpha = alpha,beta=beta, break_loop_repeat_count =
True, main_list_func = [])

    print("Component 2" , "starts")

    print("number of states", k_states_list[1])

    main_list_makine2 = machine_work(k_states_list =
k_states_list[1],alpha = alpha,beta=beta, break_loop_repeat_count =
True, main_list_func = [])

    if len(k_states_list) == 3:

        print("Component 2" , "starts")

        print("number of states", k_states_list[2])

        main_list_makine3 = machine_work(k_states_list =
k_states_list[2],alpha = alpha,beta=beta, break_loop_repeat_count =
True, main_list_func = [])

        if len(k_states_list) == 3:

            solution =
list_compare(main_list_makine1,main_list_makine2,main_list_makine3)

            compstatlist1 = compstatlist1 + main_list_makine1

            compstatlist2 = compstatlist2 + main_list_makine2

```

```

        compstatlist3 = compstatlist3 + main_list_makine3

    else:

        solution = list_compare(main_list_makine1,main_list_makine2)

        compstatlist1 = compstatlist1 + main_list_makine1

        compstatlist2 = compstatlist2 + main_list_makine2

    print(solution)

    counter = counter + 1

    if counter == 10000:

        break

print(len(compstatlist1) , len(compstatlist2),len(compstatlist2))
Results_machine1 = []
Results_machine2 = []
Results_machine3 = []
for num in range(k_states_list[0]):

    print(num)

    num_count_list1 = [state for state in compstatlist1 if
state==num+1]

    Results_machine1.append(len(num_count_list1)/len(compstatlist1))

for num in range(k_states_list[1]):

    print(num)

    num_count_list2 = [state for state in compstatlist2 if
state==num+1]

    Results_machine2.append(len(num_count_list2)/len(compstatlist2))
if len(k_states_list) == 3:

    for num in range(k_states_list[2]):

```

```

        print(num)

        num_count_list3 = [state for state in compstatlist3 if
state==num+1]

Results_machine3.append(len(num_count_list3)/len(compstatlist3))

print("Probabilities")

problast1 = []
problast2 = []

if len(Results_machine3) > 0:

    for indprob1 in range(len(Results_machine1)):

        for indprob2 in range(len(Results_machine2)):

            for indprob3 in range(len(Results_machine3)):

                print("Probability",str(indprob1) + str(indprob2) +
str(indprob3),"is",Results_machine1[indprob1]*Results_machine2[indpr
ob2]*Results_machine2[indprob3])

problast1.append(Results_machine1[indprob1]*Results_machine2[indprob
2]*Results_machine2[indprob3])

problast2.append(str(indprob1)+str(indprob2)+str(indprob3))

else:

    for indprob1 in range(len(Results_machine1)):

        for indprob2 in range(len(Results_machine2)):

            print("Probability",str(indprob1) +
str(indprob2),"is",Results_machine1[indprob1]*Results_machine2[indpr
ob2])

problast1.append((Results_machine1[indprob1]*Results_machine2[indpro
b2]))

                problast2.append(str(indprob1)+str(indprob2))

print(problast1)

```

